

Attitudes of Muslims and Christians Community of Pakistan Towards Euthanasia: A Cross Religion Study

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: August 17, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: March 18, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Attitude, euthanasia, Religion, Gender, Pakistan community</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6370184</p>	<p><i>This study investigated the attitudes of Muslims and Christian community of Pakistan towards euthanasia. This research wants to see differences in attitude towards euthanasia interm of gender among Pakistani public. Results of the study revealed that the Christians has more tolerating attitude towards euthanasia as compared to Muslims of Pakistani community. The findings also showed that gender is significant moderator between religion and attitude towards euthanasia in Pakistani society. The results of the study will be helpfullin legislation on euthanasia in Pakistan. This study will provide insight and indigenouse perspective of Pakistani society.</i></p>

Introduction

Euthanasia “The act or process of terminating of a life, usually to prevent further suffering in an incurably or terminally ill individual. Voluntary euthanasia requires the consent of a competent person who has established a valid advance directive or made his or her wishes otherwise clearly known. Involuntary euthanasia involves someone else making the decision to end someone’s life. A close family member usually makes the decision. This is generally done when someone is completely unconscious or permanently incapacitated” (APA Dictionary of Psychology, p.388). **Active Euthanasia** “direct action performed to terminate the life of a person (or animal) that is suffering greatly and is considered to have no chance for recovery. Administering a lethal injection is the most common method of active euthanasia today. This practice is distinguished from passive euthanasia, in which treatments are withheld but no direct action to terminate the life is taken” (APA Dictionary of Psychology, p.15). **Passive Euthanasia** “The intentional withholding of treatment that might prolong the life of a person who is approaching death. It is distinguished from active euthanasia in which direct action (e.g., a lethal injection) is taken to end the life. Courts have ruled that physicians do not have to try every possible intervention to prolong life, but opinions differ on where the line should be drawn. There is also controversy regarding the significance of the passive – active distinction, since both approaches result in shortening the life” (APA Dictionary of Psychology, p.767).

Review of Literature

Evenblij, Pasman, Heide, Hoekstra and Philipsen (2019) examined the factors associated with requesting and receiving the euthanasia. The study revealed ethnicity (western/Dutch), cause of death (neurological disorder/cancer), age (<80 years), involvement of pain specialist or psychiatrist and attending physician (general practitioner) are the factors positively related with receiving and requesting euthanasia while dementia, an accumulation of health problems and psychiatrist disorders are negatively relation with euthanasia.

Heide, Delden and Philipsen (2017) studied the euthanasia in Netherlands over 25 years. The research revealed that there is 18 percent increase in euthanasia from 1990 to 2015. This data showed that there is gradually accepted the euthanasia by public of Netherlands.

Kouwenhoven, Raijmaker and Delden (2013) evaluated the opinion of public and health care professionals in Netherlands after the legislation on Euthanasia. The study depicted that public and health care professionals generally support the legal requirements of Euthanasia. The research also reflected that the public showed more tolerance toward euthanasia as compared to health care professionals in Netherlands.

Munir, Afzal and Latif (2010) determined the attitude of Pakistani doctors towards Euthanasia. This study revealed that Pakistani doctors are not in favor of euthanasia because of their belief system. They were all Muslims doctors and aware with the subject.

Hains and Williams (2013) examined the attitude of health care professionals towards euthanasia in UK. The researchers found significant positive relationship between religiosity and attitude towards euthanasia among health care professionals.

Research Problem

Euthanasia is legalized in many western countries like Netherland, USA, Canada, Belgium, Colombia and UK etc but there is no legislation of euthanasia in Pakistan. This study will provide help in the preparation of legislation on euthanasia in Pakistan. This research will provide Pakistani perspective on euthanasia and highlight the comparison of gender and religious beliefs of Pakistani public on euthanasia. The findings of this study will facilitate in understanding and awareness of the phenomena of Euthanasia in Pakistani society.

Objectives

1. To compare attitudes of Muslim and Christian community of Pakistan towards Euthanasia.
2. To compare attitudes of men and women towards Euthanasia in Pakistan.
3. To assess the moderating role of Gender in the relationship between Attitude towards Euthanasia and Religion.

Hypotheses

1. There would likely to be significant difference between Muslims and Christians community of Pakistan in terms of their attitude towards euthanasia.
2. There would likely to be significant gender differences in terms of their attitude towards euthanasia in Pakistan.
3. Gender is likely to significantly moderate the relationship between religion and attitude towards Euthanasia.

Research Methodology

Participants

The cross-sectional design was used in this study. A purposive sample of 150 females (75 Muslims & 75 Christians) and 150 males (75 Muslims & 75 Christians) of Pakistani community. This sample was conveniently drawn from Lahore city, Pakistan. Age range of the participants is 35 to 55 years. Sample was calculated by G-Power analysis.

Instrument

Attitude towards Euthanasia Scale

This 10-item scale was designed to measure ATE (Naser, 2013). These centered on the medical condition ("severe pain" and "no recovery"), the locus of decision making (the "patient's request" or the "doctors' authority"), and the method of administration (actively ending the patient's life or withdrawing life support). The ATE scale has been shown to have satisfactory reliability and validity. Two reverse-coded items are included to check against response set bias from the participants. English version of the Scale was used in this research as the population was educated. Reliability of the scale on current sample is .88.

Procedure

Before data collection, the researchers contacted the Christians and Muslims community to search the participants for the study with informed consent. After taking consent, the willing participants were briefed the nature of the study. They were instructed to be honest while responding to the items of the scale. All participants were thanked at the end of each session, debriefed further about the study, and told that if a publication resulted from the collected data all personal information would be kept confidential and anonymous for this purpose.

Results and Discussion

Table 3.1

Demographic characteristics of the sample

Variables		N (%)
Religion	Gender	
	Islam	Male 75 (50%)
		Female 75 (50%)
Christian	Total	150(50%)
	Male	75 (50%)
	Female	75 (50%)
	Total	150 (50%)

The results showed that alpha reliability of attitude towards Euthanasia scale is good, Cronbach's $\alpha = .88$. This scale has 10 items, and the mean score is $M = 22.09(8.61)$. Further table indicates that the alpha reliability of its sub scale view about voluntary euthanasia is also good, Cronbach's $\alpha = .81$. The alpha reliability of its subscale, involuntary euthanasia is also good, Cronbach's $\alpha = .81$.

The first aim of the study is to investigate the differences based on religion in term of attitude towards euthanasia. The first hypothesis is that there would likely to be significant difference between Muslims and

Christians community of Pakistan in terms of their attitude towards euthanasia which is supported by results mentioned in table 3.3. Results showed that main effect of religion is significant which means there is difference in Muslims and Christians in term of their attitude towards euthanasia. Results revealed that the Christian has more accepting attitude toward euthanasia as compared to Muslims. This finding is relevant with the previous research done by Hains and Williams (2013) in which researchers found there is significant relationship between religious beliefs and attitude towards euthanasia among health professionals.

Table 3.2:

Descriptive for two-way Anova of Religion and gender on Euthanasia

Variables		<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>N</i>
Religion	Gender			
Islam	Man	21.45	9.220	75
	Woman	19.61	11.391	75
	Total	20.83	10.011	150
Christian	Man	20.60	6.910	75
	Woman	25.10	6.057	75
	Total	23.36	6.745	150

M=mean, SD= Standard Deviation, N=Total Number of Participants.

Table indicated that there are 75 Muslim Men and 75 Muslim Women. Further, there are 75 Christian Men and 75 Christian Women.

Table 3.3

Effect of Religion and Gender on Attitude towards Euthanasia

Source	<i>SS</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>η²</i>	<i>Power</i>
Religion	372.178	1	372.17	5.27	.018	.029
Gender	121.242	1	121.22	1.71	.006	.257
Religion X Gender	695.424	1	695.42	9.85	.032	.879
Error	20878.701	296	70.53			
Total	168628.00	300				

*SS=Sum of Square, df=Degree of Freedom, MS=Mean Square, η²=Partial Eta Square, p<.01**, p<.05*, p=ns*

2 x 2 Factorial ANOVA was run to examine the effect of Religion and Gender on Attitude towards Euthanasia. Result showed that the main effect of Religion $F(1, 296) = 5.27, p < .05$ is significant. Whereas, the main effect of Gender $F(1, 296) = 1.71, p = ns$ is non-significant. Further, interaction effect of Religion and Gender, $F(1, 296) = 9.85, p = ns$ is significant.

The second objective is to observe the gender differences in term of attitude towards euthanasia. The second hypothesis is that there would likely to be significant gender differences in terms of their attitude towards euthanasia, but results showed there is no significant gender difference in term of attitude towards euthanasia (see table 3.3). This result is inconsistent with the research done by Vijayalakshmi, Nagarajiah, Reddy, and Suresh (2018) in which they found gender differences on attitude towards euthanasia among nurses.

The third objective of the study is to assess the moderating role of gender between religion and attitude towards euthanasia in Pakistani society. The third hypothesis is that Gender is likely to significantly moderate the relationship between religion and attitude towards Euthanasia which is proved by findings of the study that the gender is significant moderator between religion and attitude towards euthanasia in Pakistani community (see

table 3.4). This finding is somewhat relevant with the study done by Kontaxaki, Kontaxakis, Paplos, Siannis and Christodoulou (2003) in which they found gender and religious beliefs are the contributing factors in differentiating attitude towards euthanasia.

Table 3.4

Moderating Role of Gender between Religion and Attitude toward Euthanasia

Predictor	SE	β	t
Gender	1.08	1.32	1.22
Religion	1.07	2.17	2.02*
Interaction	2.16	6.34	2.92*
R^2	.69		
F	8.28*		

$p < .05^*$, SE=Standard Error, β = Beta, R^2 = R Square,

Results indicated that Religion significantly predicts attitude towards Euthanasia, $\beta=.1.07$, $F(8.28)$ $p < .05$. The value of R^2 (.69) explained 69% variance in the Religion accounted for by Attitude towards Euthanasia. The significant interaction showed that Gender is a significant Moderator between Attitude towards Euthanasia, $t=2.92^*$.

Conclusion

It is concluded that religious beliefs and gender play considering and significant factors in differentiating attitudes toward euthanasia in Pakistanisociety. The findings of study reveal that Christians are accepting euthanasia more as compared to Muslims among Pakistani community. Gender is working as moderator between religion and attitude towards euthanasia.

Recommendations

This study will be beneficial in legislation on euthanasia in Pakistan. It will be helpful for clinical psychologist for exploring further factors related to phenomena of euthanasia. This research will give awareness to Pakistani community on euthanasia. This study will provide insight and indigenous perspective of Pakistani society.

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